

Review

Reckless or righteous? Reviewing the sociotechnical benefits and risks of climate change geoengineering

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ABSTRACT

Geoengineering options such as negative emissions technologies (NETs) or greenhouse gas removal (GGR) may need to contribute towards decarbonization, by removing CO₂ from the atmosphere and storing it safely in biological or geological sinks, or reflecting sunlight back into space via solar radiation management (SRM). Despite concerns about them, GGR and SRM are increasingly discussed as crucial complements to traditional climate change mitigation. Others routinely dismiss both SRM and GGR methods as a distraction from mitigation, or even as a potential moral hazard that induces complacency in reducing emissions. Yet, if climate impacts turn out to be more sudden and severe than currently known, such strategies could provide a rapid backstop to implement deeper emissions reductions, especially with techniques that require time to scale-up. Despite their importance and controversial status, most research on GGR and SRM remains technical, rather than social, and that knowledge of their technical characteristics remains limited, even within the physical and engineering sciences. Moreover, existing GGR and SRM options are changing rapidly in terms of their technical design, cost, and performance, and therefore scalability and deployment potential. To contribute to the debate, this study reviews and summarizes a large number of geoengineering assessments published over the past decade to document prospective benefits, but also reveal potential risks. It aims to provide a comprehensive evidence base on GGR and SRM technologies that is rigorous, timely, and interdisciplinary. This article begins by briefly defining geoengineering and associated technologies, describing how various techniques work, and summarizing recent market trends up until early 2021. Then, it discusses a series of advantages and disadvantages to these options before identifying tensions, research gaps, and a critical research agenda. It concludes with implications for research, policy, and governance.

1. Introduction

The Paris climate agreement aims to keep global temperature rise well below 2 °C, aspiring to stay below 1.5 °C above preindustrial levels on a path to “deep decarbonization” [1,2]. Negative emissions technologies (NETs) such as greenhouse gas removal (GGR) could need to contribute towards decarbonization, by removing CO₂ from the atmosphere and storing it safely in natural, biological or geological sinks. Potential methods include bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS), afforestation, as well as direct air capture and CO₂ utilization among others. More controversially, methods for increasing the Earth’s albedo, known as solar radiation management (SRM) and solar geo-engineering, have also been proposed, with stratospheric aerosol injection (SAI) the most prominent of these [3].

Despite concerns about them, GGR and SRM are increasingly

discussed as crucial complements to traditional climate change mitigation (i.e. reducing emissions) for at least three reasons. First, keeping warming well below 2 °C requires a rapid transition towards net zero emissions by 2050–2080 [4]. Climate change mitigation scenarios have consistently shown that some emission components (e.g. non-CO₂ emissions from agriculture; aviation CO₂ emissions etc.) are too hard to mitigate and may need to be compensated by GGR. Second, both GGR and SRM could buy some time for the required transition process, for example by allowing for a temporary overshoot of the remaining carbon budget. This “carbon debt” can be paid back later via net negative emissions, i.e. a net removal of greenhouse gas emissions from the atmosphere [5]. Finally, deep uncertainties around the physical science basis in climate change and tipping points in the Earth system may require emergency climate engineering options that would work on short time scales [6,7].

It is widely understood in the Integrated Assessment Modeling (IAM)

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Abbreviations and acronyms

BC	black carbon	Gt	gigaton (one billion metric tons)
BECCS	bioenergy with carbon capture and storage	IAM	Integrated Assessment Models
CCU	carbon capture and utilization	IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
CCUS	carbon capture utilization and storage	NETs	negative emissions technologies
CCS	carbon capture and storage	NPT	Nonproliferation Treaty
CDR	carbon dioxide removal	O ₃	ozone
CH ₄	methane	RFG	radiative forcing geoengineering
CO ₂	carbon dioxide	SAI	stratospheric aerosol injection
DAC	direct air capture	SMR	small modular reactor
GGR	greenhouse gas removal	SRM	solar radiation management
		TES	thermal energy storage
		VOCs	volatile organic compounds

Fig. 1. Global carbon dioxide emissions pathways under the Paris agreement, 1980-2100.

Source [15]: The figure shows the median of the 76 IPCC scenarios that limit the global temperature rise to 2 °C with 66% likelihood. Realized negative emissions are estimated by converting the BECCS energy consumption EJ/year, assuming an average biomass emission factor of 100 metric tons of CO₂ per TJ and assuming that 90% of the CO₂ is captured. The emission pledges (INDCs) in 2030 are estimated based on cumulative emissions from 2011 to 2030.

community that reaching climate stabilization at or below 2° requires “significant negative emissions” [8], but Anderson and Peters add that “negative emissions are also prevalent in scenarios for higher stabilization targets” [9]. Both the IPCC [10] as well as the European Commission [11] discuss the distinct role of GGR options for achieving net zero emissions. For example, the most recent report from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change noted that “all pathways that limit global warming to 1.5 °C with limited or no overshoot project the use of carbon dioxide removal on the order of 100–1000 GtCO₂ over the 21st century.” [12] Scenarios at the low end of this range require much more aggressive emission reductions over the next two decades facilitated e.g. through massive reductions in energy demand [13] or transformative changes in lifestyle [14]. Scenarios at the upper end are characterized by near-term emissions growth more in line with current trends. Fig. 1 shows a typical 2 °C pathway that would require the international community to safely sink 15 gigatons of global emissions by around 2080.

Solar geoengineering options—SRM—reduce the amount of absorbed solar energy in the climate system. They involve an array of methods such as SAI, marine cloud brightening, and changing the albedo (reflectivity) of land, e.g. using cover crops or white roofs. Unlike GGR, SRM does not address the root cause of climate change, atmospheric carbon concentrations. Whilst GGR shares this feature of mitigation strategies, SRM sits closer to adaptation strategies (building resilience to climate change impacts) in that it is inherently a partial solution, e.g. oceans continue to acidify.

Both SRM and GGR methods have been routinely dismissed by some

as a distraction from mitigation, or even as a potential moral hazard that induces complacency in reducing emissions [16]. Furthermore, perhaps due to these complexities and uncertainties, both GGR and SRM have become extremely controversial options. Some hail them as “magic bullets,” “emergency brakes,” and important interventions for “maintaining planetary systems”; others attack them as “taboo,” a “Promethean dream,” a “trojan horse” and a way of merely “concentrating global power.” [17–19].

Yet, if climate impacts turn out to be more sudden and severe than currently known, SRM strategies could provide a rapid backstop to implement deeper emissions reductions, including GGR methods that require time to scale-up. Indeed, there are multiple indications that climate impacts have been underestimated and could involve non-trivial “tipping points” [20]. Given these stakes, and that the pace of energy transitions to reach 2 °C or 1.5 °C are well beyond historical experience, a prudent approach requires careful consideration of all options in the fight against climate change, including SRM and other “emergency measures” [21].

Despite their importance and controversial status, most research on GGR and SRM remains technical, rather than social, political, or ecological. Fridahl et al. also warn that GGR technologies such as BECCS confront massive barriers in deployment including weak interest among investors and anticipation of high political and social constraints [22], while Nemet et al. identify a substantial innovation gap that threatens their timely adoption for meeting the international climate goals [23]. Low and Schäfer find that the feasibility of many negative emissions pathways is deeply contested, even within the IAM community [24].

Table 1
Defining mitigation, adaptation, and geoengineering terms and pathways.

Main Term	Definition	Affiliated terms
<i>Mitigation</i>	An anthropogenic intervention to reduce the sources or enhance the sinks of greenhouse gases	Carbon abatement, reducing emissions
<i>Adaptation</i>	Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities	Enhancing resilience, adaptive capacity, reducing vulnerability
<i>Geoengineering</i>	A broad set of methods and technologies that aim to deliberately alter the climate system in order to alleviate the impacts of climate change	Climate engineering, climate remediation, climate modification, climate intervention, planet hacking, GGR, SRM
<i>Greenhouse gas removal (GGR)</i>	Intentional human efforts to remove CO ₂ emissions from the atmosphere	Carbon dioxide removal, carbon cycle management, post-emission carbon management, negative emissions
<i>Solar radiation management (SRM)</i>	Controls how much solar energy reaches the surface by manipulating the planet's radiation budget to ameliorate the main effects of greenhouse gases (i.e., warming)	Solar geoengineering, sunlight reflection methods, aerosol injection, solar radiation modification
<i>Carbon sink</i>	Any process, activity or mechanism which removes a greenhouse gas, an aerosol or a precursor of a greenhouse gas or aerosol from the atmosphere	Carbon storage, carbon sequestration

Source: Author

SRM technologies are at an even earlier stage of development, where current knowledge is mainly derived from modelling studies, which are still poorly understood [25].

To contribute to the debate, this study surveys and summarizes a large number of geoengineering, NETS, GGR, and SRM assessments published over the past decade to document their pros and cons, following a comprehensive “literature review” format commonly utilized in the social sciences and executed often in the energy studies literature. Although the authors of several papers have tried to examine the state of knowledge on GGR, NETs, or solar geoengineering [26–36] none have utilized a sociotechnical lens. Other reviews take a partial focus that only include a small sample of options, i.e. work looking only at “ocean-based” options [37], or “natural climate solutions,” [38] or CDR only [39], or solar geoengineering only [40]. Moreover, very few studies tap into the rich mosaic of evidence coming from the arts and humanities or social sciences [41–46]. There remain challenges to providing comprehensive evidence on GGR and SRM technologies that is rigorous, timely, and interdisciplinary. In particular, reviews have often focused narrowly on the technical literature around costs, potentials and to some degree side-effects and failed to deal with a vast and rapidly expanding literature base.

Table 2
Exploring twelve different geoengineering options.

Type	Option	Description
<i>NETS/ GGR</i>	Carbon capture and utilization and storage	Technologies or solvents that extract, capture, transport, and storage carbon dioxide.
<i>NETS/ GGR</i>	Afforestation and reforestation	Planting trees or vegetation to absorb carbon dioxide growth.
<i>NETS/ GGR</i>	Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage	Harnessing specific energy crops (e.g., perennial grasses, or short-rotation coppicing) or increased forest biomass to replace fossil fuels as a source of thermal energy, and capturing the CO ₂ produced and storing it underground.
<i>NETS/ GGR</i>	Biochar	Biochar is obtained from pyrolysis, i.e. the thermal degradation of organic material in the absence of oxygen. Added to soils, biochar is a means to increase soil carbon stocks as well as improve soil fertility and other ecosystem properties.
<i>NETS/ GGR</i>	Soil carbon sequestration or enrichment	Growing cover crops, leaving crop residues to decay in the field, applying manure or compost, using low- or no-till systems, and employing other land management techniques to improve soil structure.
<i>NETS/ GGR</i>	Ocean iron fertilization	Uses planktonic algae and other microscopic plants to take up CO ₂ and convert it to organic matter, some of which sinks as detritus and is sequestered in the deep ocean.
<i>NETS/ GGR</i>	Enhanced weathering and ocean alkalization	Deploys physical or chemical mechanisms to accelerate the geochemical processes that naturally absorb CO ₂ at slow rates.
<i>NETS/ GGR</i>	Direct air capture	Involves a system where air from the atmosphere flows over a contactor that selectively removes the CO ₂ , which is then released as a concentrated stream for disposal or use, while the sorbent is regenerated and the CO ₂ -depleted air is returned to the atmosphere.
<i>SRM</i>	Space mirrors	Placing scatterers or reflectors of some kind in space to reduce the amount of sunlight entering Earth's atmosphere.
<i>SRM</i>	Stratospheric aerosol injection	Dispersing aerosol particles through high-altitude jets (e.g., sulfur) into the lower stratosphere, where they would reflect a small portion of incoming sunlight back to space, cooling temperatures.
<i>SRM</i>	Cirrus cloud thinning	Instead of reflecting incoming sunlight, this approach reduces cirrus cloud cover to facilitate the release of outgoing radiation.
<i>SRM</i>	Marine sky or cloud brightening	Coordinating fleets of ships to spray sea water into the air below marine clouds, thereby increasing the reflectivity and longevity of clouds.
<i>SRM</i>	Surface based brightening (i.e., albedo modification via human settlements)	Enhancing the reflectivity of buildings, roads, or other structures to cool the global temperature.

Source: Author's compilation of [53–58].

This article begins by briefly defining geoengineering and associated technologies, describing how the technology works, and summarizing recent market trends up until late 2020. Then, it discusses a series of advantages and disadvantages to those options drawn from the literature before offering a series of conclusions for energy planners, investors, and analysts.

2. Background: Grappling with “geoengineering”

Although many critical researchers object to lumping different technologies together, the umbrella term “geoengineering” or “climate engineering” commonly describes both efforts to remove greenhouse gases from the atmosphere, i.e. via GGR or CDR, as well as efforts to manage incoming solar radiation or inbound sunlight, e.g. SRM [47,48]. As Caldeira et al. clarified:

Most geoengineering approaches fall into one of two categories: carbon dioxide removal or solar geoengineering. These approaches can be viewed as part of a portfolio of strategies for diminishing climate risk and damage. Carbon dioxide removal attempts to break the link between CO₂ emissions and accumulation of CO₂ in the atmosphere. Solar geoengineering (also known as solar radiation management) attempts to break the link between

Fig. 2. Visualizing twelve geoengineering options across carbon capture and storage, greenhouse gas removal and solar radiation management.

Source [59]: Carbon capture and usage and carbon capture and storage technologies are plotted on the a) panel. Seven distinct carbon dioxide removal options are plotted on the b) panel. Five unique solar radiation technologies, or radiative forcing geoengineering, are shown in panel c). Note: CCU = carbon capture and utilization. CCS = carbon capture and storage. CDR = carbon dioxide removal. RFG = radiative forcing geoengineering. CH₄ = methane. BC = black carbon. O₃ = ozone.

accumulation of CO₂ in the atmosphere and the amount of climate change that can result [49].

As Table 1 indicates, this makes geoengineering (inclusive of SRM and GGR) fundamentally different than climate mitigation pathways, which seek to stop emissions, or adaptation, which seek to build resilience to the impacts of climate change.

Despite their relative novelty in the climate and energy policy literature compared to mitigation and adaptation, geoengineering technologies have a surprisingly long history. Researchers began exploring ways to formally modify the earth's weather during World War II and even developed weather modification techniques including cloud seeding, dispersing fog, or reducing the severity of hurricanes with silver iodide by the 1940s [50]. In 1965, President Lyndon B. Johnson's Science Advisory Committee investigated an approach to managing increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentrations by spreading small reflective particles over large oceanic areas to increase the albedo [51]. The United States even deployed some of these weather modification techniques during the Vietnam war, before they were multilaterally outlawed during negotiations with the Soviet Union and the subsequent signing of the 1976 Convention on the Prohibition of Military or Any Other Hostile Use of Environmental Modification Techniques (known colloquially as the ENMOD Convention). The term "geoengineering" in relation to addressing climate change was used in the peer reviewed

literature as early as 1977, with "marine geoengineering" gaining prominence in the 1990s and geoengineering in the atmosphere attracting attention in the mid-2000s based on support from the Nobel Laureate Paul Crutzen, who wrote about stratospheric aerosol injection [52]. This review covers *all* of these proposed geoengineering and solar radiation technologies and many more shown in Table 2, with 12 total options catalogued by their type and a short description. Fig. 2 shows how all 12 options could exist as an integrated portfolio or at least how they would involve different scales and dimensions of climate intervention.

Although Fig. 2 does a nice job placing geoengineering options across the domains of carbon capture and storage or utilization, GGR and SRM, another useful typology focuses not on what the technologies *are*, but what they *do*. Here, it is helpful to think about four very broad classes of technical options [60]. A class of *carbon sequestration options* essentially store, capture, or sink carbon or other greenhouse gas emissions into geological disposal in landforms or in the oceans, atmospheric scrubbing, ocean fertilization, and enhancement of terrestrial sinks. A class of *albedo modification options* seek to change the earth's albedo—a measure of how much light is reflected without being absorbed—by launching mirrors or reflective particles into orbit, adding aerosols to the stratosphere, enhancing cloud reflectivity, and modifying land surfaces. A class of *climate design options* (less explored in this review) are

Fig. 3. Viewing geoengineering as a sociotechnical system. Source: Author

sometimes called “terra-forming” techniques and these seek to actively control trace gas concentrations, glaciers, and photosynthesis. A final class of options (less explored in this review) seek to *reduce vulnerability* by mitigating impacts via the construction of animal migration corridors or by diverting rivers and glacial melt water in an attempt to stabilize ocean currents and sea level. This culminates in a typology of four categories of options that seek to sequester, modify, design, or reduce impacts. Because the literature focuses mostly on the first two types of *carbon sequestration* and *albedo modification*, the review explores these techniques more elaborately than *climate design* or *reducing vulnerability*, although these latter options do come up occasionally within the evidence base.

3. Integrative framework: the sociotechnical systems approach

To help understand the promise and peril of geoengineering, this article views it as a prospective sociotechnical system—looking at more than just the technical infrastructure or processes that were mentioned in the previous section. In his history of the evolution of electricity supply networks, Hughes notes that those systems gained momentum and widespread acceptance only because they become embedded in social, political, and economic realms, not just technical ones [61]. Hughes somewhat infamously referred to this as the “seamless web” of different dimensions that had to become aligned for the sociotechnical system of electricity to succeed at becoming widespread.

Consequently, the idea of a sociotechnical system helps reveal that technologies must be understood in their societal context, and that the different values expressed by inventors, managers, and consumers shape technological change. Those trying to build the system, it follows, must overcome a complex milieu of sociotechnical obstacles to reap benefits. A penchant aspect of the sociotechnical approach is its focuses on the interrelationship of linkages between elements and co-evolutionary processes, with Fig. 3 offering an illustration of the emergent sociotechnical system surrounding geoengineering, many pieces of which will be explored in this review [62].

This study utilizes a sociotechnical approach to geoengineering more practically by breaking down our analysis into four distinct categories summarized in Table 3. First comes technical or technological elements such as buildings, power plants, aircraft, satellites, and other material

Table 3
The sociotechnical dimensions of geoengineering.

Dimension	Inclusive of	Example(s)
<i>Technical</i>	Technology, infrastructure, and hardware	Sunshades, sensors, ships, power plants, balloons, aerosols, solvents
<i>Financial and economic</i>	Price signals, economic incentives, intellectual property	Capital cost of building and operating geoengineering technologies, business models and market, patents
<i>Socioenvironmental</i>	Broad social costs and benefits	Removed and stored greenhouse gas emissions, a more stable climate, integration with renewable sources of energy, negative externalities
<i>Political and institutional</i>	Geopolitics, governance, equity	National competitiveness, rivalry, weaponization, unilateral deployment, regional cooperation

Source: Author

elements. Next is financial or economic elements encompassing the cost of that technology as well local community benefits or even aspects such as intellectual property and patents. A third category is socio-environmental, and it covers how geoengineering relates to overall benefits (or costs) to society at large. A fourth category focuses on political and institutional elements including patterns of governance, verification and monitoring, and regional competitiveness.

In laying out these categories, it is not entirely coherent to argue that the lines separating “technical,” “financial,” “socioenvironmental,” and “political” dimensions are really distinct, separate classes. The entire point of systems approaches is that such impediments are seamlessly interconnected; dividing the “social” from the “technical,” or even the “economic” from the “environmental” can be overly simplistic and even analytically deceptive, since it misses the point that such factors exist in an interdependent network. Furthermore, we must beware of studies that focus only on human centered impacts and adopt an inherent anthropocentrism to examining outcomes [63]; a sociotechnical lens thus also enables one to examine transgenerational impacts of a given technology as well as impacts for all species. Therefore, it is capable of

factoring in ecological, economic, and human survival dimensions to geoengineering.

4. The future promise and benefits of geoengineering

As the sociotechnical integrative framework implies, the benefits of geoengineering systems do indeed cut across technical, financial, socio-environmental, and political dimensions, each of which are elaborated here.

4.1. Technical: Comparatively high feasibility and rapid deployment

The technical benefits of geoengineering lay in two aspects: some of them have a higher feasibility than many mitigation or adaptation options, and some of them can also be deployed very quickly.

For instance, proponents of geoengineering point to historical trends that suggest we may be past the point of no return already. CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels and industrial processes were barely discernible in 1750, but they have grown since the industrial revolution to more than 30 billion tons/year (GT/yr) in 2010 and almost 43 gigatons in 2020. It appears that we are unable to stop this trend. To avoid the most serious climate change impacts, many scientists believe that a 70% reduction of GHG emissions from 2000 levels is required by 2100 [64]. Yet, despite the development over the past several decades of policies to mitigate GHG emissions, the rate of emissions is accelerating, growing 2.2% per year between, compared with 1.3% per year between 1970 and 2000 [65]. So despite widespread alarm over the perils attributed to climate change, over the last decade, things got worse. As the IPCC remarked, “Emissions grew more quickly between 2000 and 2010 than in each of the three previous decades.” [66].

Making matters crueler, GHG emissions are projected to increase between 990 billion tons and 6.1 trillion tons of CO₂ equivalent from 2012 to 2100 [67]. Geoengineering measures thus become all the more alluring given that global greenhouse gas emissions have continued to rise despite the pledges under the Paris Accord and contrary to the commitments from many nations, countries, and cities to decarbonize [68–70]. Given the risk of climate catastrophe, and that the required pace of energy transitions to reach the 2 °C or 1.5 °C targets are beyond historical experience, many are starting to believe that new unconventional solutions must be considered, and their implications carefully investigated. Selected options such as “enhanced weathering” or “direct air capture” even now appear in classroom textbooks on how to “solve” climate change, such as Paul Hawken’s *Drawdown* [71].

Scientists contend that even if we stopped emissions today (that is, we achieved 100% mitigation), climate change would still continue because GHG molecules mix with other gases and also do not simply disappear once they are in the atmosphere. Once emitted, a ton of CO₂ takes a very long time to process through the atmosphere—according to the latest estimates, one fourth of all fossil fuel derived carbon dioxide emissions will remain in the atmosphere for several centuries and complete removal could take as long as 30,000 to 35,000 years [72]. Put another way, the climate system is like a bathtub with a very large tap and a very small drain [73]. Emissions already in the atmosphere could endure longer than Stonehenge, Mozart compositions, and perhaps outlast even high-level nuclear waste [74]. Given the knowledge that emission trends are still increasing, and existing concentrations will continue to warm the atmosphere for decades no matter what humanity does now, mitigation, the rationale goes, is an exercise in futility. Money can be better spent on engineering our way out of a wickedly warmer world.

Some geoengineering options have a very high feasibility and extremely rapid deployment times. For example, stratospheric aerosol injection could be done with today’s technology by spraying a fine mist of lightly reflective or colored particles into the upper atmosphere. Although it sounds far out (pun intended), Parson notes that in actuality “Its underlying scientific principles are well understood, as are the basic

engineering approaches by which it would be implemented. Consequently, it could be done today, albeit crudely, with current knowledge and technology.” [75] This would make the sun appear about 1% dimmer, and the sky slightly whiter and brighter, but it could also cool the Earth by about half a degree Celsius in a year or two. Another report noted that increasing the reflexivity of lower clouds is another strategy that could “cool the planet within a year or two from the onset of the intervention.” [76] The report also noted that modelling and feasibility studies both confirmed it would be possible to implement SRM approaches “with few if any major technological innovations required;” it even concluded that should it become important to cool the Earth rapidly, these technologies are the *only ways* to achieve this goal. Thus, geoengineering holds the promise of “solving” climate change and introducing rapid cooling efforts that could work in a matter of a few years, rather than decades, with very short lead times and fast reductions in temperature [77].

4.2. Financial: Low-cost climate stabilization and host community benefits

Advocates are quick to point out that geoengineering strategies, in aggregate, also offer discernible financial benefits. They claim that geoengineering is magnitudes-of-order cheaper than mitigation. Some estimates purport that a global geoengineering program can be implemented for only \$100 billion, whereas single mitigation efforts (such as building fleets of nuclear power stations, or diffusing hundreds of millions of electric vehicles) can exceed \$1 trillion or more. Morgan suggests that geoengineering approaches are likely to cost only a fraction of a percent of GDP, while the cost of mitigation will be considerably higher – at least a few percent of GDP, maybe more [78]. Another study noted that the direct cost of a SAI program managed by high-altitude jets intended to reduce the rate of global warming in half would cost as little as \$2.25 billion per year [79]. The National Bureau of Economic Research in the United States reviewed expected costs for some geoengineering options and noted that [80]:

- Dispersing aerosols by artillery guns and balloons would cost only \$20–\$25 billion/1–2 years;
- Dispersing aerosols by high altitude aircraft could be done for \$200 million to \$30 billion a year;
- Direct air capture and CDR costs could be as high as \$200 per ton at the prototype stage, but drop to as low as \$30 per ton of carbon dioxide removed once economies of scale have been achieved. (In December 2020, carbon credits on the European Trading Scheme were already higher than this, being traded at about €31).

This makes options such as SRM inexpensive compared to climate mitigation or adaptation; it also makes them options “so cheap” that they can be feasibly implemented “at any time” by all countries or even subnational groups and organizations [81]. Parson wryly notes that “climate engineering is cheap” and that “various commentators have proposed that, for considering the strategic implications of these technologies, it is a useful approximation to consider their cost as zero.” [82].

Moreover, geoengineering options can accrue significant benefits to host communities. One large review of the literature noted that afforestation, soil carbon management, enhanced weathering (on land), and biochar can all contribute to soil quality, wildlife habitat and diversity, recreational opportunities, nutrient retention and water cycling under appropriate management regimes that have significant agricultural or financial value in terms of better crop yields and contributions to local livelihoods [83]. Accelerated mineral-weathering approaches that attempt to accelerate the natural processes that neutralize CO₂ acidity could provide “substantial” benefits in terms of neutralizing some of the acidification of the ocean caused by excess anthropogenic CO₂ [84]. Biochar and afforestation can also lead to stronger bioeconomy

Table 4
Various GGR techniques and carbon potential for the United Kingdom and the World.

GGR Technique	GGR Potential (GtCO ₂ /year)		Cost (£/tCO ₂)
	UK	Global	
Soil Carbon Sequestration	0.001 to 0.031	1.5 to 2.6	-36 to 9
Biochar	0.006 to 0.041	1.5 to 2.6	-183 to 265
Afforestation/Reforestation	0.019	1.5 to 3.0	15 to 81
Enhanced Weathering	0.025 to 0.083	Up to 3.7	20 to 1299
Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage	0.017 to 0.066	2.4 to 10	29 to 203
Direct Air Capture with Storage	0 to 0.77	0 to 10+	352 to 810

Source [91].

knowledge networks that can help further regional cooperatives and create robust food and fiber supply chains; DAC and carbon sequestration can diversify livelihoods where minerals could be mined; and soil carbon sequestration can create additional sources of on-farm revenue and better farming incomes [85]. Although they note it will depend on policy design as well as scale of implementation, Honegger et al. wrote that GGR options can generate positive local and regional impacts on achieving various sustainable development targets via social, economic, political, and physical channels [86].

4.3. Socioenvironmental: Avoided emissions and integration of low-carbon energy

Central to the promise of geoengineering is its ability to deliver extremely large emissions reductions and/or displace or avoid large degrees of climate change and global warming. The Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology in the United Kingdom estimated major global potential for GGR efforts from 1.5 Gt to beyond 10 Gt of carbon dioxide per year, as Table 4 summarizes [87]. One systematic review of

the literature on NETs noted similarly massive potential: 0.5–3.6 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ for afforestation and reforestation, 0.5–5GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ for BECCS, 0.5–2GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ for biochar, 2–4 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ for enhanced weathering, 0.5–5 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ for DACCS, and up to 5GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ for soil carbon sequestration [88]. As Fig. 4 indicates, geoengineering, especially in the form of NETs, could be absolutely essential for achieving a 1.5 °C or 2 °C pathway. The National Research Council in the United States concurred, and noted that “limiting warming to 2 °C will require CO₂ emissions reduction, post-emissions consumption by GGR or some combination of these in the amounts of roughly 1000 to 3000 GtCO₂ before 2050, and 3000 to 6000 GtCO₂ before 2100.” [89] Another study notes that GGR “appears essential for limiting warming to well below 2 °C; such stabilization of global climate is a precondition for at least partially achieving the [Sustainable Development Goals]” [90].

Moving from NETs to SRM, Caldeira et al. examined six different options shown in Table 5 and noted that two of them—space-based schemes, and SAI—could achieve what they termed “high maximum” cooling potential compared to other options, and both cloud and ocean whitening could achieve “medium cooling” potential—and SAI and

Table 5
SRM methods and global cooling potentials.

Solar geoengineering method	Maximum cooling potential	Attainable speed of deployment	Relative cost per unit effect	Relative risk to environment per unit Effect
Space-based schemes	High	Slow	High	Low
Stratospheric aerosols	High	Fast	Low	Medium
Whitening of clouds	Medium	Fast	Low	High
Whitening of the ocean	Medium	?	?	?
Plant reflectivity	Low	Medium	Medium	High
Whitening of built structures	Low	Medium	Medium	High

Source [94].

Fig. 4. The large potential role of negative emissions technologies and climate change mitigation. Source [92].

Fig. 5. A hybrid renewable electricity-direct air capture integrated facility. Source [96]: Note: TES = thermal energy storage.

Fig. 6. A cost-optimal supply chain for biomass, waste-to-energy, or hydrogen-based bioenergy energy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS). Source [98].

cloud whitening would also be fast [93].

An additional socioenvironmental benefit is the potential coupling, and synergy, between some geoengineering technologies and other innovations, especially renewable energy. DAC, for instance, needs low-temperature heat of around 100 °C when utilizing solid sorbents, making it suitable for low-cost renewable electricity and heat pumps [95]. Fig. 5 shows such a hybrid DAC-renewable electricity system proposed for the Maghreb region, which could remove up to 10% of global emissions and with energy almost entirely powered by solar PV panels.

Bui et al. identify equally promising synergies between NETs technologies, especially BECCS, with bioenergy including wastes and residues, hydrogen, and combined heat and power [97]. They mapped global conversion pathways needed to generate electricity and heat for the adoption of BECCS and noted the optimality of biomass and waste combustion to provide electricity or even the pyrolysis or gasification of lignocellulosic biomass, especially wood. A diversified range of sources such as miscanthus, poplar, and various residues (wood, crops, agricultural wastes) were all available, along with municipal solid waste, all of which could be channeled into thermoelectric power plants, combined heat and power facilities, or hydrogen stations (see Fig. 6).

Other modeling work has centered on synergies between renewable electricity, hydrogen, heat pumps, nuclear power (in the form of small modular reactors, or SMRs) and DACCS. Hanna et al. projected levelized costs of carbon removal for various DAC configurations (low temperature, high temperature, and fueled by a mix of hydrogen, natural gas, nuclear fission, or renewables including heat pumps) for 2025 and 2075 [99]. They determined that low temperature systems have the lowest costs of removal (shown in Fig. 7) followed by high temperature gas systems and high temperature hydrogen systems being the most expensive. However, due to expected rates of innovation and learning, they expect such systems to perform far better by 2075. Other CDR options have similarly positive synergies with low-carbon electricity (especially solar, wind, and hydropower), or low-carbon heat (especially concentrated solar power, nuclear, and geothermal) [100,101]. Still other studies note positive synergies between NETs and renewable energy [102] as well as GGR techniques and innovation for CCUS systems [103].

Fig. 7. Projected levelized cost of carbon dioxide removal for selected direct air capture (DAC) systems in 2025 and 2075. Source [104].

4.4. Political: National competitiveness, progressive policy and regional cooperation

A final collection of sociotechnical benefits to geoengineering fall in the political realm. One benefit is that geoengineering research could deliver future technological innovations that enhance the economic competitiveness of supporting nations. As the Congressman and former Presidential Candidate Newt Gingrich said in 2008, “instead of penalizing ordinary Americans, we would have an option to address global warming by rewarding scientific invention [through geoengineering]” adding: “Bring on the American ingenuity.” [105] Indeed, geoengineering is even one of those areas where incumbent energy firms, notably those with fossil fuel supply chains centered on oil and gas, can become a part of the decarbonization process. Their capabilities already involve extraction and injection, and their infrastructure (financial, human, technological) can all be strategically reoriented to “collect and inject” [106]—keeping them in business but also meeting climate targets.

Advocates of geoengineering are also quick to point out that it is more acceptable amongst powerful stakeholder groups than mitigation or adaptation efforts are. The promise of geoengineering initiatives turns the politics of climate change “upside down” because they offer prompt, massive benefits to powerful special interest groups at seemingly minor investment costs [107]. This is in sharp contrast to mitigation or adaptation strategies that are supported by disenfranchised stakeholders but contested by powerful special interest groups. Indeed, even Nobel Laureate Paul Crutzen has stated that the lack of political progress on climate mitigation justifies sustained research on geoengineering [108]. Political scientists Kahan and colleagues also found, after surveying the perceptions of 3000 participants in a study of the United Kingdom and United States, that geoengineering had the potential to counteract the political polarization over climate change, noting that people expressed more support and open-mindedness towards geo-engineering than mitigation or adaptation [109].

Unlike mitigation options that require cooperation from all major-emitting nations, geoengineering can be undertaken unilaterally by nation-states, corporations, or even wealthy individuals. As Victor and his colleagues state, “it is cheap, easy, and takes only one government with sufficient hubris or desperation to set it [geo-engineering practices] in motion.” [110] The United States could choose to fund such a solution to save Greenland’s ice cap in order to prevent flooding in Florida, or China could choose to fund such a solution to preserve Himalayan glaciers in Bhutan, Nepal, and Tibet to secure freshwater supplies.

Although nations could act unilaterally, they could also form climate clubs or multilateral coalitions. This would be especially likely to arise if experienced and anticipated climate change harms are widely distributed worldwide, so states perceive a broadly shared peril; if states felt they had much to gain by sharing knowledge and cooperation on geo-engineering development; and if such systems were to be distributed to all actors, avoiding situations of asymmetrical or differential control [111]. Horton and Reynolds write how given climate change is a global threat, states will have strong incentives to band together to tackle it via geoengineering, and that this challenge represents “an opportunity to encourage states to cooperate globally in order to maintain their own long-term interests.” [112].

5. The risks and perils of geoengineering

The sociotechnical framework not only provides a useful tool to examine hopeful benefits; it also implies the existence of a seamless web of technical, financial, socioenvironmental, and political risks and challenges.

5.1. Technical: Immaturity, insufficiency, and impermanence

The proclaimed and anticipated benefits of geoengineering do come with some significant technical barriers including the nascency of development for some systems (immaturity), inability to fully address

Fig. 8. Achievability and carbon storage potential of varying carbon sinks and reservoirs. Source [124].

climate change (insufficiency), and the risk that such systems will only be a temporary gap measure (impermanence). And, since we have no real-world experiences with massive, earth-encompassing human catalyzed changes with these proposed technologies, we may find that there are an array of unanticipated consequences that are more negative than the benefits.

Concerning immaturity, while some options like afforestation, land management and CCUS have a longer history of development, others are very new, and technologically immature. The National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine reviewed a suite of negative emissions technologies in 2019—including blue carbon, terrestrial carbon removal, BECCS, DAC, carbon mineralization, and geologic sequestration [113]. It noted only four specific options were even close to deployment: afforestation/reforestation, changes in forest management, uptake and storage by agricultural soils, and some forms of BECCS. They also warned that only a few options were cost effective, with many having direct costs that well exceeded \$100/t CO₂. As a result, the report cautioned that the potential uptake for nets was “substantially lower” than what the IAMs suggest, and certainly less than attempts to achieve less than 2C of warming [114]. Another important dimension is supply chains—about half of the 10 Gt/y CO₂ to be achieved with BECCS globally is to be fueled exclusively with biomass waste, but this would necessitate the collection and delivery of all economically available agricultural, forestry, and municipal waste to a BECCS facility. As the National Research Council warned, “this would be logistically challenging anywhere, and especially in countries with limited organizational capacity.” [115] A follow up 2021 assessment on solar geoengineering options suggested that only three of them—SAI, marine cloud brightening, and cirrus cloud thinning—were worth considering in the report, and that of these, only SAI was mature enough to be considered for near-term deployment [116].

Concerning insufficiency, most solar geoengineering techniques would reflect solar radiation, but do little to stop emissions and thus address urgent climate change related issues such as ocean acidification [117–119]. Because surface air temperatures respond faster to radiative forcing than sea levels, there is also a risk that SRM strategies could worsen sea level rise [120]. DACCS has a sequestration efficiency only of 75–100%, meaning it is unable to capture all carbon, and BECCS has a sequestration efficiency of only 50–90%, even less if indirect land use change is accounted for [121]. Moreover, carbon removal, capacity, and storage efforts also have finite limits and thresholds—many of which would blunt their ability to store global carbon flows sufficient to stop

warming. Although many different types of reservoirs are theoretically possible (see Fig. 8), covering different timescales and varying degrees of effectiveness, Lawrence et al. calculated that many of them would be insufficient to meet the challenge of storing the sheer volume of existing emissions [122]. They caution that storage in the deep oceans would be challenging even for small amounts, due to lack of practical experience; lack of adequate geological data in some regions, as well as the trade-offs between efforts to collocate CO₂ capture sites and injection sites versus the development of CO₂ pipelines would mitigate the potential for carbon sequestration on land; enhanced weathering storage is limited by logistical requirements (mining and transport) and ecological impacts rather than by mineral rock resource availability. In sum, they conclude with a troubling outlook: “The achievability for nearly all reservoirs is qualitatively estimated to be relatively high for small amounts (e.g., <1 Gt(CO₂)), but challenging for larger amounts (e.g., >1000 Gt(CO₂)), with considerable research needed, e.g., into ecological and economic implications, and development of adequate infrastructures for extensive deployment.” As Parson concluded, these challenges with geoengineering make it “a highly imperfect corrective for the environmental effects of elevated greenhouse gases” [123].

Concerning impermanence, many of the geoengineering options discussed in the review are reversible, that is, there are conditions by which they could release their carbon and thus be very impermanent solutions. Afforestation and soil management are at the ever present risk of deforestation, illegal logging and uncontrollable, and unpredictable, wildfires. Restored coastal wetlands can be drained again, making its carbon storage temporary [125]. Although permanence for carbon mineralization would be very high for mineralization of basalt or peridotite, geologically sequestered carbon can leak from saline aquifers [126]. Even SRM techniques such as SAI are reversible in that particle injection can be “shut off” after which the aerosol particles would remain in the atmosphere only five to ten years [127]. This gives rise to the “longevity problem” [128] or “termination problem” [129] of many geoengineering approaches—once begun, we will be in their permanent debt [130] and would need to implement them continually and perpetually—for centuries at least, possibly longer.

Collectively, these concerns of immaturity, insufficiency and impermanence create great uncertainty about whether and how NETs and SRM options can be deployed, at scale, and when. Some analysts caution that this makes them overly risky technologies, a sort of gamble without any guarantees. Even subsystems needed to work with some NETs options such as carbon capture and storage or carbon capture and utilization have deep uncertainties in terms of their future cost profiles or performance attributes. As one recent study warned, “There is no guarantee that [such carbon storage options] will be deployed, and without considerable environmental risks, all other mitigation levels, including demand-side solutions, still require strong policy support and are indeed a precondition for such ambitious targets.” [131].

5.2. Financial: Prohibitive expense and restrictive patents

Opponents of geoengineering assert the opposite of the extolled financial benefits from section 4.2: that rather than being low-cost, many if not most applications are extremely costly or would depend on unrealistically high market prices of carbon. Whereas SAI (noted in Section 4.2) can be cheap, enhanced weathering could be very expensive. Drawing down 50 ppm of atmospheric CO₂ with enhanced weathering could cost \$60–600 trillion for mining, grinding, and transporting rock, with additional costs for distributing it [132]. The costs of carbon mineralization cannot yet even be predicted because fundamental data about process and engineering systems is insufficient [133].

Even though they are more established, and more often discussed in the literature, NETs have similar cost challenges. Authors of one systematic review of NETs thus warned that “costs impose further economic limits to NETs deployment.” [134] Although costs will continue to

Fig. 9. The operational Direct Air Capture (DAC) facility at Climeworks in Switzerland.
Source: Climeworks

Table 6
Energy demand estimates for various negative emissions technologies.

Technique	Efficiency (g/kWh)	TWh needed to deliver 24 Gt of CO ₂ per annum	Proportion of global energy use
Gas/seawater injection	2779	8636	9%
Supported amines	3166	7581	8%
Supported aziridine	2000	12,000	12%
Fluidized bed DAC	64	375,000	383%
Wet calcination	470	51,064	52%
Wet calcination	384	62,500	64%
Wet calcination	365	65,753	67%
Flue gas BECCS	2083	11,522	12%
Flue gas BECCS	2702	8882	9%
Flue gas BECCS (2050)	4478	5360	5%
Ocean liming	827	29,021	30%
Electrochemical HCl removal	827	29,021	30%
Electrochemical ocean liming	662	36,254	37%

Source: Modified from Ref. [144]. Note: DAC = direct air capture. BECCS = bioenergy with carbon capture and storage. HCl = hydrogen chloride. kWh = kilowatt-hour. TWh = Terrawatt-hour. Gt = gigaton.

evolve and involve future uncertainty, Creutzig et al. cautioned that “all NETs have substantial costs” and depend on “some sort of carbon pricing,” in some cases as high as \$100 to \$200 per ton now but up to \$1000 to \$4000 per ton by 2100 (e.g., BECCS); DACCS has future costs in the range of \$100 to \$300 per ton in 2050 [135]. The National Academies concurred, noting that “the primary impediment to several NETs is high cost” and explaining that the only existing commercial DAC, run by Climeworks (see Fig. 9), captures CO₂ at a reported cost of \$600 per ton [136].

A final financial challenge concerns the intellectual property behind geoengineering technology and potentially anticompetitive behavior with patents. Chavez examined patent trends for geoengineering and suggests that even though research is in its infancy, the patenting of related innovations has grown considerably in a short period of time [137]. However, Chavez also cautioned that the characteristics of those patents “might deter access to this technology, potentially stymieing

future climate-engineering innovation,” given that many such patents were artificially broad and could block future developments. He also warned that such patents were being hoarded by a small number of patent holders; that the United States Patent and Trade Office process was time consuming (with some applications taking more than 80 months to approve); and that a “patent land grab” was ongoing that could consolidate patents and promote anticompetitive behaviour. He expressed concern that in sum this widespread distribution of broad, overlapping patents causes various problems, such as those stemming from “patent thickets” or “anticommons.” [138].

5.3. Socioenvironmental: Energy intensity, mitigation deterrence, and environmental degradation

Sitting in sharp contrast to the benefits elaborated in section 4.3, the socioenvironmental risks and challenges of geoengineering identified in the critical literature include the fact that many options are themselves energy intensive (affecting global energy supply patterns sharply); that they can reduce efforts at climate mitigation; and that they can also result in their own host of environmental calamities.

In terms of energy intensity, some forms of geoengineering would require gargantuan amounts of energy, with Table 6 breaking down the numbers for some options. It notes that some such as fluidized bed direct air capture could require more than 380% of global energy use to deliver 24 Gt of carbon dioxide removal. Another study found that a global enhanced weathering industry that sequesters 1 Gt CO₂-C per year could have energy requirements approaching 0.7–19.4% of global energy consumption [139]. DAC systems would also need additional energy sources, especially if they were to remain carbon neutral; for instance, for the United States alone to sequester about 13 Gt of Co₂ per year, it would need to deploy solar PV across 100 million acres of land [140]. Another review similarly found that both BECCS and DACCS “heavily impact energy production” and would require 450 Exajoules of electrical energy per year by 2100 as well as 400 EJ of non-electrical energy [141]. Modeling by Hanna et al. suggest that by the year 2075, hydrogen based DAC systems could consume more energy (250 Exajoules) than the world did in 2017; even options using waste heat, heat pumps, or various renewables could surpass 150 Exajoules per year (see Fig. 10) [142]. Hanna and colleagues calculated that the total energy consumed to attain that removal for various DAC configurations would

Fig. 10. Net carbon dioxide removal and projected energy use for selected direct air capture (DAC) technologies in 2075. Source [143].

most likely reach 9–14% of global electricity use in 2075 (median; 5–30%, 15th/85th percentiles) and 53–83% of global gas use in 2100 (median; 0–470%, 15th/85th percentiles).

Another way of looking at it are the energy requirements per removed ton of carbon dioxide; again, these are quite high, with DACCS needing 6.7–10 GJ of energy (depending on assumptions) per ton removed [145]. To put this into perspective, burning or combusting 100 gallons of gasoline releases only about 13 GJ (and also emits about a ton of carbon dioxide) [146]. Troublingly, some geoengineering will rely on high-temperature processing systems that may be best suited for fossil fuel combustion (e.g., coal or coke) rather than renewable energy (e.g., heat pumps or solar panels) [147].

Because of such energy intensity, some geoengineering options are therefore carbon intensive as well. McQueen and colleagues recently reviewed the state of the art for CDR options and noted, worryingly, that all of them require electricity, process heaters and dryers, and thermal energy to run compressors, air separation units, and condensers [148]. Moreover, they noted that the sociotechnical systems supporting CDR involve ample opportunities for carbon dioxide to be released into the environment—via energy combustion or feedstock use, via transportation, and via utilization or sequestration (see top panel of Fig. 11). They also calculated that no current solvent-based direct air capture system is carbon neutral or net-zero, instead those fueled by natural gas have substantial carbon equivalent emissions (see bottom panel of Fig. 11) and even those powered by solar, wind, nuclear, and geothermal have both direct and embodied emissions. Systems powered by hydrogen fare no better in terms of resource efficiency—one assessment estimated that a DAC-hydrogen system would consume 4.7 tons of water for every ton of carbon dioxide captured [149].

A second major concern is the risk that because geoengineering is seen as silver bullet, it greatly reduces the incentive to invest in other pathways, notably climate mitigation. This has become termed a “moral corruption” [151] or “moral hazard par excellence” [152] as well “mitigation deterrence.” [153] McLaren even notes that the ability for geoengineering to create “mitigation deterrence” could involve multiple forms: one is “substitution and failure,” where geoengineering substitutes for mitigation but never delivers; one is “rebounds,” which includes unanticipated side effects from land use change or oil recovery facilitated by captured carbon dioxide; one is “imagined offsets” where expected reductions in carbon never materialize [154]. These three forms of mitigation deterrence are presented in Fig. 12, with McLaren

warning that all three together could account for an additional temperature rise of up to 1.4 °C.

A third major concern relates to the negative environmental impacts of geoengineering options themselves—and these could be prodigious, and involve not only (deliberate) changes in climate but also deforestation and land use in addition to biodiversity loss as well as water consumption. At the top of the list would likely be how to govern the extremely large *waste flows* (or stored carbon) that would need to be safely managed for hundreds to thousands of years [156]. Moreover, the National Academies warned that “Mining minerals that spontaneously bind CO₂ would create enormous volumes of waste rock that may contaminate water and/or air.” [157] In terms of *climatic change*, because many geoengineering options block sunlight and counteract heating that occurs at the Earth’s surface, it would on a large scale result in a global climate that is drier than our normal climate. Such climatic changes could create large and unknown alterations in regional and seasonal climates [158]. Furthermore, because forests established at high latitudes decrease albedo, afforestation/reforestation at high latitudes would run the risk of inducing net warming despite the cooling caused by the forest’s CO₂ uptake [159]. Forests established in regions with limited rain could have adverse effects on streamflow, groundwater resources, as well as natural irrigation patterns [160]. Cloud albedo enhancement runs the risk of interfering with mesoscale atmospheric and oceanic systems, such as the West African Monsoon and the El Niño Southern Oscillation [161].

In terms of *land use*, Creutzig et al. caution that “BECCS is highly land intensive” and that “land use requirements are illustrative but crucially depend on yields, technology, and soil productivity.” [162] That said, BECCS would require high-energy crops including willow and poplar that would need to be deployed at extremely large scale—to displace only 3.3 Gt of carbon dioxide per year, these crops would need to be planted on 7–25% of agricultural land and 25–46% of arable plus permanent crop area [163]. To put this in perspective, both BECCS as well as afforestation and reforestation would have demands on land 2–4 *times* larger than land identified as abandoned or marginal, meaning deployment would invariably interfere with food production and land preservation; BECCS could also consume up to 75% of global annual nitrogen fertilizer production [164]. Other projections put the numbers even higher, noting that BECCS alone may require almost *all* current cropland area to meet climate targets [165]. Fig. 13 attempts to project the energy, land, and water requirements for various NETs options

Fig. 11. The carbon intensity of carbon dioxide removal techniques (top panel) and direct air capture options (bottom panel). Source [150]: Note: For the top panel, solid lines represent material flows, dashed lines electricity or thermal energy flows.

Fig. 12. Carbon pathways and budgets accounting for “mitigation deterrence” by 2100. Source [155]; Note: GGR = greenhouse gas removal. MD = mitigation deterrence.

Fig. 13. The land, energy, and water requirements for various negative emissions technologies to reach a 2 °C target. Source [169]; BECCS = bioenergy with carbon capture and storage. DAC = direct air capture. EW = enhanced weathering. Water use is displayed in km³ yr⁻¹.

(including BECCS, DACCS, and enhanced weathering) to reach a 2 °C target and the numbers are staggering, with land use requirements reaching one billion hectares per year or water requirements in excess of one thousand cubic kilometers per year. Afforestation and soil management also suffer from active attempts at logging, deforestation, and soil degradation [166]. Indirect land use change as well as land ownership and access issues could relate to all other geoengineering options [167]. Essentially, geoengineering in this manner can be interpreted as a global system that transfers environmental risk from the climate or atmosphere to the land [168] it redistributes the risk, rather than eliminating it.

In terms of biodiversity loss and environmental destruction, widespread

deployment of BECCS could suck up so much land that they decimate terrestrial species and forest losses that exacerbate species extinction [170]. Mining minerals that spontaneously bind CO₂ would create enormous volumes of dust and possible air pollution [171]. Ocean fertilization runs the risk stimulating phytoplankton species capable of releasing toxins in tropical, subarctic, and Southern ocean waters [172]. In tropical areas, afforestation is likely to cause changes in local and regional energy balance and hydrology, soil chemistry and acidity, along with impacts on soil carbon storage; new forests could also emit volatile organic compounds (VOCs), which increase cloud condensation nuclei and affect cloud formation [173]. Methods of engineering carbon capture and storage could involve chemical sorbents and materials with unknown and long-lasting effects on ecosystems. In their wide-ranging review of SAI, cirrus cloud thinning, and marine cloud brightening, the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine cautioned that these options could interfere with a multitude of environmental systems, including [174]:

- Continued deep ocean warming even if reductions are achieved via SRM to surface ocean warming;
- Increased ocean acidification via lowered ambient temperatures and the enhanced solubility of carbon dioxide in ocean waters;
- Increased air pollution in pristine areas as stratospheric sulfate aerosols reach the surface as acid rain;
- Altered loss of sea ice and stratification of water columns leading to decreases in ocean net primary production and ocean circulation;
- Damaged terrestrial vegetation via changes in temperature and precipitation patterns and alterations in transpiration, CO₂ fertilization, and soil respiration;
- Resultant sudden and unexpected changes in temperature and precipitation with the potential to fragment “climate niches” within some rainforests and change animal migration patterns.

Other work has suggested that SAI could engender unwanted changes in precipitation patterns as well as depletion of the ozone layer [175].

Fig. 14. Tradeoffs between carbon storage, evaporative cooling, and changes in albedo across different forest types. Source [186].

5.4. Political: Governance failure, colonialist dependence, and geopolitical disparity

The final sociotechnical challenges and risks facing geoengineering fall into the political realm. Broadly conceived, these relate to governance, dependence, and disparity.

In terms of governance, the literature strongly suggests that geoengineering will only “work” as long as actors abide by climate norms and rules about proper deployment—a critical concern because lax oversight would lead to ineffective climate stabilization, wasted resources, and the collapse of public confidence [176]. However, existing governance architectures for geoengineering are weak—no direct treaty regulates or governs their deployment, unlike for example nuclear power and its related Nonproliferation Treaty (NPT). Governance is strong currently only in three areas covered by other international agreements: afforestation and reforestation (covered under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change), saline aquifer storage (various drinking water acts), and ocean fertilization (the

London Convention and London Protocol). This makes governance and especially monitoring and verification over the entire suite of geoengineering options fragmented, confusing, and often nonexistent.

In terms of dependence, the fact that many geoengineering technologies are being financed, experimented on, and deployed in wealthy and industrialized countries (the Global North) rather than poorer and developing countries (the Global South) raises concerns of colonialism and piracy. According to this logic, some of the most severe risk of geoengineering are related not necessarily to its environmental or technical aspects of deployment, but its political reinforcement of unsustainable social and economic structures, ones that resist reforming industrial society, or addressing pressing issues of poverty and global inequality [177]. It also means that geoengineering can be depicted as an act of neocolonialism that merely preserves patently unjust international political relationships, with rich countries hoarding benefits, and poorer countries suffering unevenly all of its risks. Power over managing the global side effects of geoengineering rest in the hands of a few wealthy nations—geoengineering will free rich and highly emitting

Fig. 15. The constantly varying “optimal” roles and levels of responses to climate change. Source: Top panel is from Ref. [189] Bottom panel from [190].

countries from their historical climate debt, while simultaneously burdening poor and low-emitting ones. Some also identify what they see as a pattern of intellectual colonialism in that knowledge production around geoengineering remains heavily dominated by major research institutions (and the interests backing them) in Europe and North America, making it what one study calls a “rich man’s solution.” [178] Knowledge and capabilities remain concentrated mostly in industrialized countries, perpetuating “hidden politics” and inequalities in decision making authority, the argument runs, and also shaping the types of research projects undertaken in the first place [179].

6. Discussion: tensions, research gaps and a critical research agenda

The sociotechnical framework not only offers a comprehensive lens by which to appreciate the promise and challenges facing geoengineering, it also reveals at least four critical research gaps, including the need to: better explore tensions and tradeoffs, broaden

geoengineering cases to include the Global South, examine more dynamic portfolios or cocktails of deployment, and pursue more interdisciplinary research designs and methods.

6.1. Tensions, tradeoffs and diverging governance regimes

As with other mitigation and adaptation strategies, geoengineering options have positive synergies and negative tradeoffs, both with each other and with broader sustainable development goals [180]. For example, manipulating oceanic absorption rates will influence acidity levels that, if altered in a short period can severely compromise the health of marine habitats. Some GGR techniques in particular have very long timeframes and depend upon large geographic-scales that would require almost perfect operation [181]. Consequences on water demand for the production of biomass and of energy due to the extended use of combustion-based technologies that require cooling could have severe implications for biodiversity through large-scale biomass plantations [182]. Affordable and universal nutrition, for instance, might be

Table 7
Governance tensions in four climate pathways.

	Mitigation	Adaptation	Greenhouse gas removal	Solar radiation management
<i>Timing</i>	Costs now, benefits delayed	Costs whenever, benefits may be relatively soon after	Costs now, benefits delayed	Costs now, benefits now
<i>Temporal Incidence</i>	Costs now, benefits to later generations	Benefits mostly to the generation bearing costs	Benefits mostly future generations	Benefits mostly to the generation bearing costs
<i>Geographic Incidence</i>	Local costs, global benefits	Local costs, often relatively local benefits	Local or broader costs, global benefits	Local costs, local and global benefits
<i>Sectoral Incidence</i>	Focus on emissions from energy consumption	Very heterogeneous	Focus on energy-intensive industries (cement, iron and steel) and power plants	Only a few options are likely to garner political support
<i>Relation to Uncertainty</i>	Must act early despite greater uncertainty	May act later after reducing uncertainty	Must act early despite greater uncertainty	May act later after reducing uncertainty
<i>Governance Issues</i>	Dominated by national goals and international negotiations	Dominated by state and local agencies, but need for coordination is great	Dominated by traditional energy companies and those with significant storage capacity	International oversight needed because of possible actions of rogue nations and individuals acting on their own

Source: Author.

threatened by bioenergy competition for land. Minimum energy access and energy poverty might similarly be threatened by the wide-scale roll out of direct air capture, creating enormous pressure on energy systems.

Conversely, positive synergies might also be plausible, through ecosystem restoration, or lowered local heat stress from albedo modification. For instance, by cooling sea surface temperatures and reducing both the frequency and intensity of marine heat waves, some evidence suggests that SRM options can reduce the vulnerability of tropical coral reefs to climate change—and reduce the threat of mass “bleaching” and widespread reef mortality [183]. As another example, the global adoption of diets lower in meat could enable diversion of land away from fodder crops to bioenergy, helping make BECCS more affordable [184].

Forestry in particular (and options such as afforestation, BECCS, or soil enrichment) underscores the ability for particular efforts to entail a mix of both negative and positive synergies, or risks alongside benefits. Both the types of a forest as well as its form of management will determine the extent to which a given area can store carbon, support evaporative cooling, or positively (or negatively) change albedo (see Fig. 14) [185]. Promoting geoengineering in tropical forests could store extremely large amounts of carbon, but increase the risk of that stored carbon to drought or effects on clouds and precipitation. In boreal forests, low surface albedos may even outweigh the benefits of carbon sequestration. For temperate forests, afforestation may sink carbon, but effects on albedo and evaporative forcing are uncertain and unclear. All three forest types could also see their carbon stores or gains suddenly reversed due to sudden insect outbreaks or wildfires.

Moreover, the socially optimal level of geoengineering is dynamic—a constantly moving target—and will perpetually change based on active levels of mitigation, investments in adaptation, and even the deployment of other GGR or SRM options. Fig. 15 (top panel) shows already how effective mitigation and adaptation strategies require different temporal, geographical, and sectoral scales, and how investment in each reduces the need (in theory) to invest in the other [187]. Fig. 9 (bottom panel) shows how ideal investments on climate mitigation will depend on the degree of geoengineering and adaptation deployed [188]. Changing a single portfolio or pathway, or intervening with a new technique in this complex adaptive system can potentially alter the optimality of all other options.

The tendency for many geoengineering options to be fast, cheap, but imperfect also generates acute tensions in governance. Used wisely, geoengineering can accrue into a well established contingency plan to a future climate emergency; it can also be used earlier and less intensely, to shave the peak off projected near-term heating while a serious mitigation effort is ramped up, thereby reducing the cost of a global transition to climate-safe energy sources; or it can be targeted to reduce specific high-priority regional or seasonal risks, such as the loss of Arctic sea ice. But used recklessly or incompetently, it may make all of these aspects much worse. Its utility depends on how it is governed [191]. As

Parson concludes, geoengineering presents “new needs, and new challenges, for governance and control, to pursue the benefits and minimize the harms they hold.” [192] Table 7 showcases some of the governance tensions across all four pathways of mitigation, adaptation, GGR, and SRM.

Consider four potential tensions in practice. Accelerating learning and innovation in geoengineering would undoubtedly improve performance and make such options cheaper; but the cheaper they become, the more problems of control arise because geoengineering options become more accessible to nonstate actors including rogue nations or even terrorist groups. Affordability lies in direct tension with security. Current geoengineering experiments are often done at very small scales to minimize risk—making them safer for the environment—but this also makes it more difficult to scale up such experiments or generalize from them at larger sizes (e.g. beyond pilots to deployment across cities, regions, and even entire nations). Risk management lies in direct tension to scaling. Most SRM options work by reflecting more solar radiation back into space—but this could have negative effects on renewable energy production, particularly from concentrating solar power, on Earth [193]. Global cooling lies in direct tension with one form of electricity decarbonization. The urgency and immediacy of addressing climate change creates a strong incentive to deploy geoengineering options as soon as possible—but this also means there will be fewer tests, possibly less stringent safety protocols, and greater uncertainty about their impacts. Urgency lies in direct tension to safety.

6.2. Broadening the set of geoengineering cases

Future geoengineering research could improve by exploring a broader variety of “cases”, that is, more focus on SRM (which remains understudied in comparison to GGR) as well as more cases and experiments from beyond Europe and North America.

This is particularly important given that SRM options do not resonate with climate mitigation efforts in the same way that most NETs or CDR efforts do. In other words, the global climate science community has developed relatively robust understandings of how risks to various critical systems are reduced as one reduces GHG concentrations in the atmosphere. Deliberations concerning most NETs fit easily within this discourse. SRM options cannot be cogitated in the same way, because they do not scale with global temperature and instead have risks that entail other environmental attributes such as humidity, precipitation, and surface energy balance [194].

The unique attributes of SRM compared to NETs suggest that it needs to be carefully studied across a range of different contexts and conditions. And yet, currently research on geoengineering may remain marginalized in the Global South and developing world [195]. There have been only a few attempts to expand public debate about geoengineering beyond the Global North; fewer projects and less funding in

Fig. 16. Visualizing simultaneous deployment of GGR and SRM pathways.

Source [200]: Note that the top arrow refers to SRM approaches such as albedo enhancement and sunshades, whereas the bottom lines represent GGR approaches such as bio-char, direct air capture, and ocean fertilization.

the Global South; and an underrepresentation of actors from the Global South in geoengineering discussions, meetings, and workshops [196]. Such comparative work and inclusion could help researchers, policy-makers and other stakeholders to better prioritize efforts for geoengineering development towards opportunities that are more feasible in different time frames, and more likely to yield societal or financial benefits.

6.3. Cocktails and complex portfolios

As mentioned in Section 5, geoengineering methods could raise serious ethical concerns and issues of moral hazard, ethics and justice – coordinating mitigation pathways with these technologies now could

“lock-in” their use for future generations, despite manifold side effects and risks. And yet most geoengineering research focuses on a single technology (e.g., biochar or DACCS) in a single region (e.g., California or Europe). It does not adequately capture the reality of how geoengineering options would most certainly be deployed as a part of portfolios where dozens of different technologies would likely be utilized simultaneously (See Fig. 16) across multiple scales (even transnational ones). Long and colleagues call this the urgent need to study “cocktail geoengineering,” [197] others talk about the necessity of studying “portfolios” of NETs [198,199].

And yet our understanding of how to model, anticipate, and capture such complex portfolios and cocktails is only nascently materializing, given that many models have major constraints and make overly

Table 8

Potential conflicts between geoengineering options when deployed as a portfolio.

Dimension	Solar radiation management	Greenhouse gas removal
Focus	Does not address cause of human-induced climate change (high atmospheric GHG concentrations).	Addresses the cause of human-induced climate change (high atmospheric GHG concentrations).
Risk	Introduces novel global risks, will be judged largely on risk criteria	Does not introduce novel global risks, will be judged largely on cost criteria
Cost	Inexpensive to deploy (relative to cost of emissions reduction).	Currently expensive (or comparable to the cost of emission reduction).
Temporality	Can produce substantial climate effects within years.	May produce only modest climate effects within decades.
Governance	Raises difficult issues with respect to global governance.	Raises fewer and less difficult issues with respect to global governance.
Reversibility	Could be implemented suddenly, with large-scale impacts before enough research is available to understand their risks relative to inaction.	May be implemented incrementally with limited effects as society becomes more serious about reducing GHG concentrations or slowing their growth.
Cooperation	Could be done unilaterally.	Requires cooperation by major carbon emitters to have a significant effect.
Path dependence	For likely future emissions scenarios, abrupt termination would produce significant consequences	For likely future emissions scenarios, abrupt termination would have limited consequences

Source [205].

Fig. 17. Differentiating between carbon capture and storage (CCS, top panel) and carbon capture and utilization (CCU, bottom panel). Source [208].

simplistic assumptions about geoengineering [201,202]. In their comprehensive review, Fuss et al. noted that for the IAM community, there was a need to better understand “integrated portfolios of NETs in IAMs, which should include an evaluation of interactions with other mitigation options and effects of NETs on non-climate sustainable development goals” as well as “a better understanding of geophysical

constraints of negative emissions and implementation in IAMs” and lastly “analysis of NETs deployment dynamics in a risk management framework, acknowledging that many decisions in climate change mitigation will have to be made in the short term and therefore under uncertainty.” [203].

A part of more careful and nuanced work concerning portfolios and

cocktails is to better handle the inherent differences within classes of NETs and SRM options. Indeed, Table 8 shows that conflicts can occur between GGR and SRM techniques. Morrow et al. capture this thinking succinctly when they write it is imperative that researchers “split, don’t lump.” [204] That is, move beyond technology-level assessments that treat all options as roughly equal in terms of their potential, or their impacts, or their policies, making it difficult to distinguish optimal ones from suboptimal and even undesirable ones.

This notion of splitting or critically differentiating technologies also emerges from the literature on the carbon storage and sequestration side of the geoengineering discussion, with a compelling case made to distinguish between options that use carbon capture and storage, or CCS, and carbon capture and utilization, or CCUS. Although these two options have some similar technical attributes, they also differ considerably in their business models, sustainability impacts, and social dynamics (see Fig. 17) [206]. In CCS, CO2 emissions from industrial flue gases are captured and then sequestered permanently underground. But in CCU, CO2 is used as resource, e.g., for the production of chemicals and materials, and can at least partially replace conventional fossil resources. Storage in these products is only temporary and the carbon is often emitted to the atmosphere [207].

6.4. Towards interdisciplinary, multi-method modeling approaches

A final gap and potential priority for future geoengineering research is to move towards interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary, and multi-method efforts. As implied based on Sections 4 and 5, few studies reveal insights that cross more than one or two of the four sociotechnical categories we identify: technical, financial, socioenvironmental and political. Moreover, much work remains centered within the natural and physical sciences community, rather than the arts, humanities, and social sciences more broadly or work inclusive of non-scientific partners.

This is unfortunate, as in part, greater integration across insights could occur through multi-method approaches. For example, while modeling efforts are dominated by IAMs, “simulation” energy-economy models can instead be used to represent what consumers and

stakeholders may actually do in a given policy context, given their preferences and perceptions [209]. Even more novel is to develop studies that directly integrate empirical data from surveys and interviews (as noted in the previous subsection) with models of geoengineering deployment that in turn simulate the technical, economic and environmental impacts of such systems. Most comprehensive of all would be a study approach that adds in a higher level, institutional component to represent the system-level transformative effects of geoengineering options across varying geographies and pathways—a theme that cuts across the suggestions offered in Sections 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3.

These thoughts all bely the necessity of interdisciplinary work that blends together the physical and natural sciences with engineering and economics as well as a central role for the social sciences, arts, and humanities. The National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine recently reaffirmed the utility of interdisciplinarity research agendas in the space of solar geoengineering because the topic bridges across so many areas of expertise [210]. Political scientists and demographers are needed to better understand the range of socioeconomic or geopolitical background conditions driving options. Behavioral scientists are needed to understand emerging norms and resulting actions that could significantly shape the effects of geoengineering deployment. Engineers and applied scientists will need to innovate new technology designs such as the specifications of airplanes, nozzles, precursor chemicals, and logistical protocols. Chemists, physicists, and material scientists will have to better comprehend the processes that follow if reflective material is released into the environment, including radiative effects, lifetime, and decay. Ecologists, biologists, and life scientists will need to study interactions between geoengineering and biological organisms and entire ecosystems. Economists and other social scientists (notably ethicists) will need to deliberate on how geoengineering pathways affect welfare and also change the quality of life or quality of health for various populations.

Interdisciplinary work would be strengthened by a commitment to transdisciplinary alliances (the inclusion of non-academic or non-scientific partners such as civil society groups, business firms, regulators, etc. [211]). One model here could be examples of transdisciplinary

Table 9
The contrasting promises and peril of geoengineering.

	Promising prospective benefits	Perilous potential risks
<i>Technical dimension</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers rapid climate change abatement in a world where neither mitigation or adaptation can adequately address climate change Some options (e.g., stratospheric aerosol injection) could be done with today’s technology and deployed in a matter of a few years 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Would not address all fundamental changes in climate or threats such as ocean acidification Only a few options ready for deployment, most would be years to even many decades away; and even then, would need to be deployed in perpetuity for hundreds if not thousands of years
<i>Financial dimension</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Portfolios using some options (aerosols) could be deployed at the cost of only a few hundred million dollars to \$25 to \$30 billion, compared to the need to invest trillions of dollars in climate mitigation efforts, other options (DACCS) already cost-competitive with carbon prices in the European Union Some options (e.g., afforestation, reforestation, soil recycling, BECCS) could contribute to local improvements in the environment and also generate much needed revenue for farms and otherwise deprived rural areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some options (e.g., enhanced withering) could cost as much as \$600 trillion alone; some NETS would require prices as high as \$4000/ton of carbon by the year 2100 Anticompetitive patent behavior, including patent thickets and overly broad patents, could deter and slow innovation trends or consolidate benefits among only a few large firms
<i>Socioenvironmental dimension</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can deliver extremely large emissions reductions on par with the Paris Accords and consistent with a 1.5–2° temperature pathway Could bolster investments in other coupled sociotechnical systems (e.g., renewable electricity, carbon capture and storage, nuclear power, bioenergy, hydrogen) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many options are themselves energy intensive and could come to consume very large amounts of energy themselves (e.g. up to 10 GJ of energy per ton captured and stored, or up to 19.4% of global energy consumption or 53–83% of global gas use) Can reduce efforts at climate mitigation and promote “mitigation deterrence,” as well as resulting in their own waste streams as well as a host of environmental calamities to land, water, climatic change, and local habitats and forests including the species that depend on them
<i>Political dimension</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can expedite and facilitate future technological innovations that enhance the economic competitiveness of supporting nations Does not necessarily rely on multilateral governance initiatives, and can instead be deployed quickly by single nation states and even sub-national actors (i.e., it is not prone to the tragedy of the commons). That said, could also stimulate regional cooperation and different geopolitical clubs and coalitions of countries with aligned geoengineering interests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weak governance structures and lack of monitoring and verification could give rise to misuse and even weaponization of the technologies Raises concerns of colonialism, piracy and dependence on large firms or actors in the Global North, at the expense of the Global South

Source: Author

“action research” from other disciplines and areas [212–216], especially those that focus on reducing vulnerability, improving equity outcomes, or aligning research programs with pro-poor or poverty reduction schemes. Geoengineering research needs input not only from scientists but also agricultural leaders, educators, religious leaders, citizens in general and even students. It may very well be that new institutions need to be created (perhaps a dedicated agency at the United Nations, or perhaps a new international treaty) to help steer and govern geoengineering developments. Such institutions might benefit from being both interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary by nature.

7. Implications and conclusion

What are we to make of these conflicting aspects of geoengineering—that it brings the promise of substantial benefits only at a considerable risk? Do its advantages outweigh the disadvantages? Should we completely reject geoengineering? No, not necessarily. Instead, this section of the study presents four more nuanced findings.

First, geoengineering brings measurable prospective benefits as well as discernible potential risks summarized by Table 9. Possible benefits include rapid deployment to address climate change with (some forms of) technology readily available and cheap; considerable economic and social amenities to host communities; synergizing and boosting the renewable energy sector and some low-carbon innovations; and enhancing national competitiveness and regional cooperation on climate change. Possible tangible risks include technological immaturity, insufficiency, and impermanence; high financial costs for some options as well as anticompetitive economic behavior; greatly increasing global energy consumption and interfering with mitigation efforts; and

exacerbating already unequal relationships between Global North and Global South.

Further obfuscating matters, though, these costs and benefits are not distributed evenly. As Fig. 18 depicts, some risks would begin to occur even before the technologies are deployed—such as subnational actors seeking to pursue weaponized designs, or firms hoarding intellectual property and patents. Some benefits and risks, such as economic development or water contamination, would occur now or as soon as the technologies were deployed, while others, such as climate change or declining production and profit margins, will occur well into the future. They also occur at different scales: the land, air, and biodiversity impacts associated would often be localized, whereas the systemic changes in global climate would be worldwide. And they occur to different actors: landowners, local producers, entrepreneurs and investors might benefit in the Global North, whereas those in the Global South or suffering land degradation or water scarcity suffer. In this way, geoengineering never addresses fully all climatic or global warming risks, it just redistributes them, and essentially transfers many of them from the atmosphere to the land.

Second, and also indicated in Fig. 18, geoengineering operates as a sociotechnical system, one that cuts across various stages of the technology (research, construction, deployment, waste streams) as well as different governance needs. If the purported benefits of geoengineering are to be achieved, then strong governance principles need to be put in place, now, so they materialize. These include strong protections against patent hoarding, the promotion of sustainable forestry, coupling with low-carbon energy, a commitment to climate mitigation and an active consideration of waste management. In this way, successful geoengineering is not a given; whether it leads to denuded forests, collapsed

Fig. 18. Sociotechnical risks, governance attributes, and benefits of global geoengineering. Source: Author

communities and impoverished environmental wastelands or vibrant energy-independent and carbon-neutral societies is a matter of proactive governance.

Third, because of its contested complexity, we can expect geoengineering to have very dispersed development trajectories globally. In other words, an era of geoengineering, if there ever is one, will neither be uniform nor entirely predictable. Because it involves a cocktail of different options with very different deployment dynamics and technological attributes, the particular array of benefits and risks will emerge differently at each location, shaped by a multitude of factors including geology and hydrology, type and location of technology, corporate governance, regulation related to waste discharges and transportation, the price of energy, the carbon intensity of energy, patterns of finance and intellectual property, and social demographics. We already see some of this divergence between countries expressing interest in SRM—with China and the United States likely to suffer severe impacts of climate change, and investing in solar geoengineering, but countries such as France, Russia, and Germany abstaining; countries such as Bangladesh and those in Southern Europe might like to invest in SRM, but lack the capacity [217]. The future will likely hold even more diverse and divergent geoengineering pathways than these.

Fourth and lastly, because of this complex and often contestable nature of geoengineering—that it is both ethnically reckless or morally righteous to different stakeholders—the debate may be impossible to resolve, since both advocates and opponents can point to an array of data supporting their claims, and simply ignore countervailing data that they do not like. Consequently, geoengineering reminds us that climate change and low-carbon transitions, especially those to net-zero or a net-negative society, involve not only material infrastructures and government regulations but also politics and values; and current geoengineering pathways guarantee perhaps an inevitable clash between local and global interests, between entrepreneurs and environmentalists, between climate policy but also economic and security policy. Those leasing their land for projects are at times pitted against those condemned to possible downstream pollution, and advocates of various energy systems (renewable, fossil fueled, nuclear) that are expected to provide the mammoth amounts of energy to fuel a geoengineering economy may compete with each other. And so if one is to look for but one certainty within this intrinsically unpredictable topic, geoengineering will over the coming decades likely remain deeply divisive.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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